

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TRANSFORMATION OF UKRAINIAN UNIVERSITY PRACTICE DUE TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGY ENHANCED LEARNING

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Abstract

The research highlights the importance of use of ICT in contemporary higher education system. Due to the development of technology enhanced learning the quality of higher education becomes competitive in the European labor market. Meeting the high standards, it requires considerable changes within the University education practice, basically in the normative organization structure. The normative organization documents are to regulate e-learning within particular higher education establishment.

Keywords: e-learning, regulation, open University, monitoring, organization structure, hybrid University

Due to the rapid development of ICT the use of e-learning in higher education system became of considerable importance. Thus, its significance is stated in the Decree of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine "Regulations on distance learning" (2017) [1]. This document outlines the main goal and tasks of distance learning. Its purpose is to provide educational services through the use of modern information and communication technologies in education at certain educational or educational qualification levels in accordance with state education standards; according to the programs of preparing citizens for admission to educational institutions, training foreigners and improving the qualifications of employees.

Effective modernization of the content and organizational structure of higher education is a successful step in implementing the tasks of the government of the country regarding the organization of open education. An integral component of open education is e-learning, which is implemented through the distance learning system as part of the country's education system, with a regulatory and legal basis, an organizational structure, staff, system-technical, logistical and financial support, which implements e-learning at the higher level, post-graduate education, lifelong education, as well as self-education. Guided by the President's Order on the "Regulations on Distance Learning", e-learning centers were started to be organized on the bases of higher education institutions, which required clear coordination.

The main task of e-learning is to provide citizens with the opportunity to exercise the constitutional right to obtain education and professional qualifications, improve their qualifications regardless of gender, race, nationality, social and property status, type and nature of occupations, worldview beliefs, party affiliation, attitude to religion, religion, state of health, place of residence according to their abilities.

The document outlines:

- 1) ways of implementing e-learning (its application separately and in combination with other forms);
- 2) rules for the organization of the educational process according to the distance form of education (the

form of the educational process (individual work, educational classes, practical training (in universities), assessment measures); types of educational classes (lecture, seminar, practical classes, laboratory classes, consultations and others), which are provided remotely in synchronous or asynchronous mode according to the curriculum; receiving educational materials (video, audio, graphic and text information in synchronous or asynchronous mode);

- 3) rules for organizing the educational process using distance learning technologies (categories of the population; types of educational activities using ICT; additional distance learning technologies in the system of inclusive and professional-practical education);

- 4) scientific and methodical support of distance learning, as well as taking into account the need to improve the qualifications of scientific and pedagogical workers and methodologists of educational institutions regarding the organization and ownership of distance learning technologies) [2].

According to the specifics of the organization of open education, higher educational institutions are divided into open and hybrid types. In hybrid ones, alongside with the traditional, there is a distance form of education. Today in Ukraine, most higher education institutions are of mixed type.

In open higher education institutions, studying is organized virtually, via the Internet. There is only one institution of this type in Ukraine - Open International University of Human Development "Ukraine".

Its normative document that regulates the activity of the institution is "Regulations on the Organization of the Educational Process at the Open International University of Human Development "Ukraine" (2015). According to the Regulation, the main directions of the University's activities are: training of specialists of various educational and qualification levels; training and certification of scientific, scientific and pedagogical staff; scientific research work; specialization, retraining of specialists; advanced training; cultural and educational, publishing work; preparation for University admission and course study [3].

It should be emphasized that the goal of this University is to provide education to people with limited physical capabilities, therefore the main directions of the institution's scientific and research work are: development of effective concepts for the rehabilitation of the disabled people; study of the international experience of rehabilitation of this category of people; creation of training programs for people with disabilities; development of projects of special enterprises capable of using the labor of this population group.

The main tasks of the University include: implementation of educational, scientific and technical, creative, and health activities; training and attestation of scientific and pedagogical staff; studying the demand for certain specialties on the labor market and promoting the employment of graduates; ensuring cultural and spiritual development of the individual.

The organization of the educational process is carried out within the University, its regional institutes, colleges, branches, etc. (see figure 1).

Fig. 1. Organizational structure of the Open International University of Human Development "Ukraine"

The educational process is carried out in the following forms: practical classes, independent work of students, tutorials, assessment measures. The main types of classes are: lecture, laboratory, practical, seminar, individual class, consultation, which can be individual or group, depending on the physical, sensory or social limitations of the students.

Participants of the educational process are: students, listeners, scientific and pedagogical, medical workers, coaches.

Regarding the organization of the educational process, it should be noted that at the University you can get a bachelor's and master's degree in the following specialties: human health, document studies and information activities, design, philology (Ukrainian language and literature), philology (translation), psychology, international relations, publishing and editing, journalism, law, marketing, finance and credit, biology, ecology, environmental protection and sustainable use, computer engineering, electronic devices and systems, food technology and engineering, transport, social work, tourism, hotel and restaurant business.

Distance learning at the University is regulated by the Principle on the Organization of the Educational Process at the University "Ukraine" using distance technologies. Its implementation takes place on the Moodle platform, where more than 1,500 distance courses are presented, each of which consists of methodological recommendations, theoretical material, a

workshop for practicing the skills and abilities of applying theoretical knowledge, reference material, knowledge evaluation and control system. Each course is built on the basis of a curriculum that forms a modular system. Studying on distance courses takes place in 3 stages:

Stage I – introductory session (face-to-face/distance);

Stage II – guided independent work (remotely);

Stage III – final session (face-to-face).

Quality assessment of students' skills and knowledge is ensured by providing evaluation measures (incoming, current, final assessment).

Therefore, using the principles of e-learning, the University fulfills one of the main tasks of modern education - providing knowledge to all those who want it due to the flexibility and accessibility of the learning process.

Thus, the current trend of organizational transformations in Ukraine in the framework of e-learning is the creation of a national information and communication infrastructure through a series of measures: the creation of state institutions and structures for the organization and implementation of e-learning, ICT support for higher education, training of staff to work in the open education system [4].

Regarding the technological foundations of e-learning in the universities of Ukraine, the most important features are the following: the introduction of

technological equipment taking into account the specifics of a particular subject and specialty; development and implementation of student-centered learning methods; development of criteria and technologies for ensuring high quality e-learning; provision of opportunities for continuous professional development of teachers working within open education programs [5].

References

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